

**ASSESSING PRONGHORN DISTRIBUTION, MOVEMENTS, AND HABITAT USE IN
NORTHEASTERN CALIFORNIA**

Annual Report – 2015/2016

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Pronghorn were studied on the Modoc Plateau in northeastern California from 2014 through 2016 to examine movements, reproduction, habitat use and factors affecting survival of adult females and fawns. During the course of the study we radio-collared and 48 adult females and 42 fawns and followed them until their death or the end of the study. After excluding four capture-related mortalities from analyses, overall annual survival for adult females was 69% ($\pm 7\%$), which is low compared to other pronghorn populations. Mountain lions accounted for 62% of all mortalities and 80% of all predation-related pronghorn deaths. Most (61%) adult mortalities occurred during the summer immediately following the peak birthing period, when adult females are seeking out more secluded areas to hide their fawns. This behavior, coupled with juniper woodland expanding into the sage-steppe habitat on the Plateau, may increase predation risk to pronghorn by increasing the ability of ambush predators, like the mountain lion, to remain undetected during their approach.

Fawn mortality was similar across the two years where fawns were radio-collared, with a 57% overall mortality rate. All fawn mortalities occurred within 35 days of collaring (median = 9 days), and unknown causes (37.5%) or suspected coyote predation (21%) accounted for most of the deaths. Fawn survivorship from our collared sample was generally higher than reported in other studies.

We used approximately 247,000 point locations collected from GPS collars to examine pronghorn movements and habitat associations on the Modoc Plateau. On a landscape level, adult pronghorn avoid forest year-round, and riparian areas depending on the season. While use of conifer woodlands was always low, it was greater in the spring. On a home range scale, pronghorn used locations that were, on average, less obscured by tall shrubs, in areas that had less shrub cover, more forbs, were 25 m higher in elevation than nearby random locations, and were more likely to be coincident with recent livestock activity. In contrast to observed habitats used during most of the year, females bedded fawns in areas with both short and tall shrubs. Tall shrub coverage at bed sites was similar to random locations, while low shrub coverage at bed sites was substantially greater than at random locations. Selection of fawn bed sites with greater tall shrub coverage may explain the greater association females had with conifer woodland habitats during the fawning season.

Daily movement patterns were greatest from noon to 1900 hours, averaging about 400 m/hr. While activity was recorded during all hours of the day, movement was least during the early and late morning hours. Few migration events were noted in the winter of 2014/2015, possibly due to a more mild winter, but most radio-collared females shifted their home ranges during the winter of 2015/2016. Migration movements ranged from very quick range shifts that occurred over a few days, to shifts that spanned several days or even weeks.

The combination of vital rates observed in this study predicted a long-term growth rate of $\lambda=0.95$, corresponding to a 5% annual decline in the population, and matched the observed population trajectory from 1993-2003. Population growth was by far the most sensitive to changes in adult survival. While a relatively small increase in adult survival is projected to lead to a growing population (i.e., $\lambda>1.00$), fawn survival would require an increase of at least 27% above our observed survival to allow for $\lambda\geq 1.00$, a rate which exceeds pronghorn fawn survival from any other study reported in the literature.

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INTRODUCTION

The population of pronghorn (*Antilocapra americana*) in northeastern California is poorly studied (Yoakum and Koch 2009). Most data are associated with winter and summer herd counts, nutrition and habitat selection studies (Ferrel and Leach 1950) or from animals translocated to sites in central and southern California (Koch and Yoakum 2002). The estimated population size ranged between approximately 1,800 and 3,000 individuals for the period between 1956 and 1970 and then grew to almost 6,000 animals between 1971 and 1978, with the largest numbers of animals found in the Likely Tables, Clear Lake and Lassen herds. By 1992, the population had grown to an estimated 8,000 animals before undergoing a decline of nearly 50% after the winter of 1992/1993. The large reduction of the pronghorn population in northeastern California during the

winter of 1992/1993 would, by itself, be worthy of concern. However, the continued decline over the next 10 years and apparent inability of the population to recover over the past 20 years (Figure 1) suggests widespread, persistent conditions that need to be understood to facilitate recovery actions and provide for greater hunting opportunities.

Figure 1. Pronghorn population index in northeastern California, 1953–2016. The index was calculated as the sum of pronghorn counted from aerial surveys over five units from 1953–2004 and from surveys over 2–3 units from 2005–2016. Different units were omitted in each year from 2005–2016.

Declines in pronghorn population numbers elsewhere have been associated with high fawn mortality (Sievers 2004), severe winters, and extended drought conditions (Simpson et al. 2007). Factors affecting population recovery may include: reduced forage availability (Kie et al. 1980), disease (Dunbar 1999), predation (Wittmer et al. 2005, Jacques et al. 2007), severe winter weather, and drought or other climatic events (Post and Stenseth 1998, O’Gara and Yoakum 2004). Some factors, particularly climatic variables, may only act on populations in some years, making them difficult to detect in single-year studies. Factors such as predation or demographic stochasticity may have stronger effects in smaller herds associated with habitat fragmentation (i.e. Allee effects; Murray Berger and Conner 2008). Habitat fragmentation may also prevent migration between optimal wintering and breeding grounds (Hailey et al. 1966, O’Gara and Yoakum 2004). Resource competition with mule deer (*Odocoileus hemionus*) and domestic livestock, especially sheep (O’Gara and Yoakum 2004), means that increases in population sizes/stocking rates of these species could reduce forage availability for pronghorn.

The California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) and the Institute for Wildlife Studies (IWS) initiated a collaborative study of pronghorn ecology in Modoc and Lassen Counties in March 2014 to investigate factors that may have prevented the pronghorn population from recovering after the severe decline in 1992/1993. From 2014–2015, 30 adult female pronghorn were monitored with satellite Global Positioning System (GPS) collars and 24 pronghorn neonates were monitored with VHF radio-collars to examine survival, movements and habitat use. Results from 2014 and 2015 suggested adult female pronghorn survival was relatively low compared to studies elsewhere, primarily due to high predation risk from mountain lions (*Puma concolor*) (Duquette et al. 2015). Toxicology results revealed 36% ($n = 28$) of adult females in 2014 and

2015 had suboptimal concentrations (<0.08 ppm) of selenium and 71% ($n = 17$) of adult females in 2015 had suboptimal concentrations (<0.70 ppm) of copper. Pregnancy rates (88%) and spring-summer survival of neonates (54.2%) were in line with results from other studies (Canon et al. 1997, Barnowe-Meyer et al. 2011). Several adult females showed movements indicative of migration between seasonal ranges, primarily in the winter of 2015-2016, but many remained in the same range year-round in 2014-2015, likely because drought conditions in the winter led to fewer snow events and failed to trigger migration to winter ranges.

Efforts in the past year of this project have focused on determining if the main conclusions above— that adult survival is atypically low due to high mountain lion predation pressure, fawn survival is adequate to support a growing population in the absence of high adult mortality, and that only a small fraction of the population exhibits seasonal migration among historic summer and winter home ranges— were robust to year to year variation in environmental conditions (e.g., climate conditions, or fluctuations in predator or alternative prey populations). This report summarizes data collected from project commencement to 30 November 2016, and includes information on adult female nutritional condition, survival, mortality factors, habitat selection and movements. Also included are data for fawns, which include survival, bed site habitat selection, and cause-specific mortality. Finally, we present data on herd composition, population growth and discuss factors that may be impacting that growth. We did not examine pregnancy rates in 2016 due to a combination of earlier results suggesting that pregnancy rates were high even in drought years and that population growth was little influenced by pregnancy rates.

STUDY AREA

Project activities occurred in Modoc and Lassen counties (Figure 2; 41.4872° N, 120.5425° W). Land cover within the study area comprises 41% forest, 37% shrubs, 10% grassland, 5% agriculture, 2% barren ground, 2% development, 2% open water, and 1% wetlands based on remotely sensed land cover data (USGS 2014). Human development is primarily low-density residential and agricultural. Livestock are common throughout the area both on private ranches and free-ranging on public lands. Trees are mostly evergreen (e.g., western juniper *Juniperus occidentalis*), but numerous species of deciduous trees occur within the area. Invasive plants (e.g., medusahead grass [*Taeniatherum caput-medusae*] and cheat grass [*Bromus tectorum*]) are common throughout the area. Elevation ranges from 1,263 to 2,470 m above sea level. Densities of linear water sources (e.g., streams and agricultural ditches) are 0.97 km/km². Densities of primary and secondary roads, and tertiary roads are <0.01 and 1.04 km/km², respectively. From 2000–2015 annual temperature ranged from -0.8–20.4°C (Figure 3) and mean annual rainfall and snowfall was 24.5 cm and 43.0 cm, respectively (NOAA 2016). Potential predators of adult and fawn pronghorn in the study area include: bobcat (*Lynx rufus*), coyotes (*Canis latrans*), mountain lions, red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), domestic dog (*Canis familiaris*), and golden eagle (*Aquila chrysaetos*).

Figure 2. General study area (yellow dashed line) and specific areas of research focus (bolded labels) of the pronghorn ecology project within northeastern California (inset).

Figure 3. Mean monthly total precipitation (blue line) or temperature (yellow line) in Alturas California, 2000–2015. Data summarized from: NOAA (2016). Two-year mean precipitation and temperature during 2014–2015 are shown with dashed lines for comparison with cumulative records.

METHODS

Adult female capture

Adult female pronghorn were captured using aerial net-gunning from a helicopter conducted by Leading Edge Aviation, Inc. through a contract with the CDFW. Once a female was netted and the helicopter landed, a handler immediately removed the netting, and subsequently restrained, blindfolded, and hobbled the animal. The handler began monitoring rectal temperature of the female to provide indication of physiological stress. If the captured female was within safe temperature range (37–39 °C), the handler fitted the female with either a battery or battery+solar-powered GPS collar (Sirtrack®, Havelock North, NZ) and collected a blood sample. The GPS collar was fit to the upper-neck of the female to minimize slipping, with two fingers of space between the collar and neck. Fecal and hair samples were collected for physiological stress analysis and genetic banking, respectively. Hind foot length was measured as an indicator of body size (citations in Martin et al. 2013), and the female was classified into one of the following age classes: fawn, yearling, 2 years-old, ≥3 years-old based on incisor eruption and molar wear patterns (O’Gara and Yoakum 2004). After the female was released, the handler recorded the geographic coordinates and general area of the capture location (Figure 2): Clear Lake, Devil’s Garden, Likely Tables, Aiden, or Smoke Creek.

Physiological stress and nutritional condition

During handling, up to 35 mL of blood was collected from each adult female. These samples were provided to the CDFW veterinarians on-site. The CDFW Wildlife Investigations Laboratory processed blood samples and provided IWS with the serology and toxicology results. We primarily focused on concentrations of blood serum selenium and copper in 2015, and selenium only in 2016. Suboptimal concentrations of selenium

(<0.08 ppm) and copper (<0.7–1.2 ppm) can predispose pronghorn to mortality, including predation and capture-myopathy (O’Gara and Yoakum 2004, Barboza et al. 2009).

Fawn capture

We located fawns by searching areas where GPS-collared female pronghorn had clustered locations from the previous day and by searching opportunistically during other activities. To ensure we did not interrupt the maternal bonding period, we did not capture fawns until ≥ 6 hours after birth (O’Gara and Yoakum 2004), based on direct observation or presence of moist amniotic fluids on the body. We strived to keep capture and handling time less than 15 minutes to reduce stress to fawns and the risk of abandonment. We minimized transfer of human scent to fawns by wearing fresh nitrile gloves during handling and keeping fawn collars and ear tags in plastic bags with native vegetation. To reduce scent transfer no more than two people were allowed to handle a fawn.

Cluster searches— We monitored the movements of GPS-collared female pronghorn daily during the anticipated fawning period (mid-May–early July). The GPS collars were programmed to collect a location every 15 minutes during this period to facilitate locating birth sites. We determined if a fawn had likely been born based on a distinct cluster of locations within a 24-h period. When a potential birth site was identified, 1-3 people went to the site and attempted to locate the associated GPS-collared female. If the female was located, we attempted to determine if she had a fawn with her. If no fawn was observed, we located the cluster site and began to search for a fawn within a 100-m radius. We searched for signs (e.g., matted and wet vegetation) of the birth site and checked all possible fawn hiding locations (e.g., under shrubs). If no fawns were found within 100-m of the cluster, we expanded our search in the direction of the GPS-collared female, as fawns are often between the mother and the cluster. We spaced ourselves so that we could see 100% of the terrain between adjacent searchers and moved toward the collared female. We searched for fawns up to approximately 200 m from the cluster site and if no fawn(s) were located, we repeated this process covering all of the area within a 200-m radius of the cluster. If no fawn(s) were located, we increased the radius to 400-m and searched that area in a less-systematic fashion. Since pronghorn typically bed twins nearby to each other, but not at the same location (Van Vuren et al. 2013), we searched for siblings within 400 m of any fawn we located. If we observed a predator in the area, we paused our search efforts until the predator was observed leaving the area. We discontinued a search if no fawns were found within 2 hours, based on our search efforts in 2015 (Duquette et al. 2015) and on other neonate ungulate studies (e.g., Carstensen et al. 2009).

Fawn handling—Fawns were captured by hand and using fish landing nets. We placed fawns in pillow cases to minimize stress during handling and used it as a blindfold during times the head was not required for measurements or samples. We weighed the fawn in the pillow case to the nearest 0.2 kg using a spring scale (Pesola® model 93750). We fitted fawns with an expandable radiocollar (model M4210, Advanced Telemetry Systems), and a green sequentially numbered ear tag (Q-flex® 1.0 tags) which was placed about 2/3 down the middle of each ear between the blood vessels (Figure 4). We monitored rectal temperature and immediately released the fawn if the temperature was outside the safe range (37–39 °C). If temperature was safe, and total handling time had been less than 15 min, we used a flexible measure tape to measure fawn body length, chest girth (Figure 5) and right hind foot length. Body length was measured from tip of nose to the intersection of the first vertebrae of the tail. Chest girth was measured

Figure 4. Neonatal pronghorn fit with a numbered plastic ear tag, Modoc County, California, 2016.

immediately posterior to the front legs. Right hind foot length was measured from the tip of the calcaneum to the tip of the hoof. We used calipers to measure new hoof growth following established methods (Haugen and Speake 1958; Brinkman et al. 2004). Hair samples were collected between the scapulae for genetic banking and we recorded the presence of any ectoparasites. We recorded the fawn behavior as “unable to stand”, “slightly wobbly”, or “very sturdy” as an index of age. We released the fawn (Figure 6) at the capture site in a direction away from any obstructions (e.g., fence) or roadways and we recorded total handling time. Upon departing the area we recorded GPS coordinates and land cover type(s) at the point where the fawn was born or bedded.

Figure 5. Neonatal pronghorn released with an expandable radiocollar and ear tags, Lassen County, California, 2016.

Figure 6. Measuring the chest girth of a neonatal pronghorn, Modoc County, California, 2016.

Resource selection

We evaluated resource selection by female pronghorn at two spatial and two temporal scales. First, to assess which habitat variables determined where pronghorn are found within the study area (i.e., second-order resource selection, *sensu* Johnson 1980), we compared known locations of collared animals to random locations within the study area where no use was recorded during this study (“unused”). Second, to determine habitat variables that influenced how adult females used different areas within their home-ranges or bedded their fawns within their home ranges (i.e., third-order resource selection, *sensu* Johnson 1980), we compared known locations of collared animals or fawn bed sites to locations ≤ 2 km from used locations where no use was recorded during this study (“unused”). We assessed both measures of habitat selection at annual and seasonal temporal scales to better understand variation in use of resources by pronghorn.

Landscape-scale resource selection

For our analysis we used 246,787 GPS collar locations (Figure 7) collected from 11 adult females captured in 2014 ($n = 69,260$), 17 adult females captured in 2015 ($n = 113,451$), and 17 adult females captured in 2016 ($n = 64,076$) from one day post-capture to 31 July 2016, mortality, or censor date. To define the area of resource availability, we plotted a 100% minimum convex polygon (MCP) encompassing all used locations. We then used the Geospatial Modelling Environment (Version 0.7.1.0, Beyer 2012) to generate an equal number of unused random locations for each female within the MCP that did not overlap any used locations.

We assessed eight resources (Table 1) related to movement barriers or mortality risks (forest, riparian habitat, and roads) and food or cover (agriculture, elevation, grassland-herbaceous, and shrubs) to determine factors influencing landscape-scale use by adult females. Roads were categorized into two classes. One class included primary and secondary roads which are generally divided and paved highways within the interstate highway system, with primary roads typically differentiated from secondary roads by presence of a median. The other class included tertiary roads, which are non-divided roads, including paved and non-paved roads, and which connect primary or secondary roads. We used land cover categories (agricultural, forest, grassland-herbaceous, and shrub) from raster-based land cover data. We used a spatial join in ArcGIS 10.2 (ESRI 2013) to attain estimates of each resource for each used or unused location and exported these data to a spreadsheet.

Figure 7. Global positioning system collar locations ($n = 246,787$) of 45 adult female pronghorn captured in 2014 ($n = 11$), 2015 ($n = 17$), and 2016 ($n = 17$) from one day post-capture to 31 July 2016 or censor date. Pink ovals indicate areas where pronghorn were captured. Yellow dashed line indicates approximate boundaries of the 100% minimum convex polygon of locations.

We used Pearson’s correlation coefficient to assess pair-wise correlations between variables (Zar 1999). When two resources were correlated ($r \geq \pm 0.50$) we excluded the one which was most correlated with other resources and standardized all remaining resource variables to z-scores and centered scores to provide equal weight for comparison across models (Zar 1999). We used program R 3.2.1 (R core team 2016) to produce a generalized linear model for each resource variable using a maximum likelihood estimator and binomial distribution. We considered used (1) and unused (0) as the binomial response variable and each of the eight resource variables and an interaction term of season and year as fixed effects (Gillies et al. 2006).

We assessed resource selection during annual (January-December), spring-summer (April-September), and fall-winter (October-March) periods. These periods were based on typical weather patterns in the study area that dictated the phenology of vegetation, which may drive shifts in pronghorn resource use and predation risk.

Table 1. Resource variables used to assess landscape-level resource selection of adult female pronghorn in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016.

Resource (unit)	Description	Source
Distance to nearest primary/secondary road (m)	Measure of the distance from a used or unused location to the edge of the nearest primary or secondary road	United States Bureau of the Census (2013)
Distance to nearest tertiary road (m)	Measure of the distance from a used or unused location to the edge of the nearest tertiary road	United States Bureau of the Census (2013)
Distance to nearest riparian habitat (m)	Measure of the distance from a used or unused location to the edge of the nearest stream or river edge	United States Bureau of the Census (2013)
Elevation (m)	Land elevation at the used or unused location	United States Geological Survey (2013)
Forest (locations)	Forest with >75% trees that are >5 m tall and >20% of total vegetation cover	United States Geological Survey (2014)
Shrubs (locations)	Vegetation consisting of trees or shrubs <5 m tall	United States Geological Survey (2014)
Grassland (locations)	Vegetation consisting of >80% graminoid or herbaceous plants	United States Geological Survey (2014)
Agriculture (locations)	Areas with agricultural practices, including cropland and pasture	United States Geological Survey (2014)

Home range resource selection

We characterized resources used by adult females based on a subsample of GPS points, and for all neonatal bed sites. For adult females we randomly selected one daytime (06:00–20:00) and one nighttime (20:01–05:59) GPS location from the most recent 24-hour period. These time range cutoffs were used as a general average of sunrise and sunset times across the year in Alturas, CA. We recognize that seasonal change in day length led to some locations being misclassified as day or night, but this approach allowed us to standardize selection of locations for surveys. We attempted to survey locations of each female at least once per month.

We attempted to pair an ‘unused’ randomly-selected location with each adult female or neonatal bed site where resources were characterized. To select paired sites, we followed a randomly-determined bearing for 2.0 km, the mean daily movement of GPS-collared adult females, and conducted a habitat survey at this location. We selected the closest location on the bearing if the exact 2.0 km location was inaccessible. We did not survey paired locations when other field activities (e.g., fawn monitoring), limited time, or weather conditions affected road access to those points. Mean distance between paired sampling sites for adult female locations was 1.85 km (SE = 0.19) and for bed sites was 2.0 km (SE = 0.24).

We collected data on 18 resource characteristics related to predation risk, nutritional condition, resource competition (i.e., livestock), or movement barriers (Table 2). We sampled within a 70-m radius of a selected adult female ‘used’ GPS point, neonatal bed site, or unused location. The 70-m radius used is based on the typical distance from which female pronghorn monitor their fawns at bedding sites (Byers and Byers 1983). We estimated horizontal structure occluding the mean shoulder height of adult females (99 cm, white panel; Figure 8) and fawns (53 cm, red panel; Figure 8) by placing the cover board at the sampling location. We moved 2 m (coyote detection distance of fawns; Byers and Byers 1983) directly north from the survey point and estimated the percent of red panel obstructed as viewed from 50 cm (mean coyote shoulder height; J. Duquette, unpublished data). This process was then repeated for the white panel at a distance of 70 m. We repeated these steps for each cardinal direction and the mean percent cover value was calculated.

Along each 70-m transect we recorded presence or absence of shrubs, graminoids, forbs, cheat grass, and medusahead grass in 4-m long sections, starting at 0, 20, 40, and 66 m. We recorded shrubs, graminoids, forbs, or juniper trees with ≥ 1 leaf or branch crossing the vertical plane of transect segment. We then

Figure 8. Estimating percent of horizontal structure covering the mean dimensions of a pronghorn fawn (red) or adult female (white) from the mean shoulder height (top of stick) of a coyote.

calculated an index of the abundance of each plant category at the site as the number of 4-m segments where it occurred divided by a maximum possible value of 16. The 70-m transects also served to divide the plot into quadrants.

We counted the total number of juniper trees and old-growth juniper trees in each plot. Old-growth trees were identified by physical characteristics such as crown shape as described by the US Forest Service (USFS 2008). We recorded elevation at selected locations using a GPS receiver. We used a range finder to estimate

the distance from the selected location to the base of the nearest juniper tree or fence in each quadrant and then calculated the mean distance of four measurements. We measured the diameter-at-breast-height of the nearest six juniper trees to the selected location. We recorded whether a plot contained at least one fence, and counted the number of fences within the plot that were passable (i.e., lowest wire $\geq 16''$ from the ground) and were not passable for pronghorn. Next, we recorded whether the site area had active agriculture practices (e.g., cropland) or had signs of recent use by livestock (e.g., fresh feces or tracks).

Table 2. Resource variables used to assess the home range resource selection of adult female pronghorn in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016.

Resource (unit)	Grouping
Elevation (m)	Predation risk
Horizontal cover-53 cm (% covered)	Predation risk
Horizontal cover-99 cm (% covered)	Predation risk
Livestock (% locations)	Nutritional competition / Predation risk
Fence present (% locations)	Movement barrier
Distance to fences (m)	Movement barrier
Fence passable (Yes or No)	Movement barrier
Active agriculture (% locations)	Nutritional condition
Cheat grass (% transects present)	Nutritional condition
Medusahead grass (% transects present)	Nutritional condition
Graminoids (% transects present)	Nutritional condition
Forbs (% transects present)	Nutritional condition
Old growth juniper trees in plot (count)	Nutritional condition
Juniper trees DBH (cm)	Nutritional condition
Shrubs (% transects present)	Nutritional condition / Predation risk
Juniper tree distance (m)	Nutritional condition / Predation risk
Juniper trees in plot (count)	Nutritional condition / Predation risk

We used Pearson’s correlation coefficient to assess pair-wise correlations between variables (Zar 1999) and removed variables with the most correlations or those we believed less influential to pronghorn resource selection. Eleven variables were moderately or strongly correlated ($r = -0.50-0.79$) with one or more other variables (Appendices B, C) and six were not considered for analysis because they were representative of similar variables (e.g., fence presence and distance to fence).

For analysis of adult female resource selection, we used package *lme4* (Bates et al. 2011) in program R 3.2.1 (R core team 2016) to produce a generalized linear mixed-effects model for each habitat characteristic using a maximum likelihood estimator and binomial distribution. We considered used (1) and unused (0) locations as

the binomial response variable and each of the selected resource characteristics and season as fixed effects with individual nested within capture year as a random effect to control for behavioral and environmental differences, respectively (Gillies et al. 2006). Juniper counts were highly skewed, with most plots having zero juniper, a few plots having 1-8 juniper, and a few plots having 20-80 juniper. We therefore looked at juniper abundance using a Fisher Exact test for the proportion of plots with >8 trees (hereafter, heavily wooded).

As with the landscape assessment we evaluated home range resource selection during annual (January-December), spring-summer (April-September), and fall-winter (October-March) periods.

We also characterized livestock fences across the study area opportunistically to assess the proportion of fences unsuitable for pronghorn passage. We primarily collected fence data near the general capture or use areas of GPS-collared adult females. Fences were categorized by landowner, number of wires, wire type (e.g., barbed), and distance of lowest wire to the ground. Fences with the lowest wire of any type $\geq 16''$ from the ground was considered 'pronghorn passable' and all other types were considered 'unpassable'.

Mortality Causes

We assessed mortality causes of adult females and fawns in the field using evidence found on (e.g., bite wound spacing; Figure 9) or near (e.g., predator tracks) the carcass (Table 3). We also considered other environmental conditions possibly related to mortality, such as recent weather. We recorded a pronghorn as being scavenged post-mortem when wounds without hemorrhaging were observed. We listed mortalities as probable predations when evidence on the carcass (e.g., bite wounds with hemorrhaging) indicated a predator was likely the final cause of death. However, our ability to determine cause of death was occasionally hindered by post-mortem circumstances (e.g., high temperatures and scavengers) that complicated our ability to separate pre-mortem and post-mortem factors. When we could not confidently assign a mortality cause, we sent carcasses in suitable condition to the CDFW Wildlife Investigations Laboratory for necropsy.

Figure 9. Assessing cause specific mortality of a pronghorn by referencing predator canine spacing (yellow arrow) and wound hemorrhaging (yellow circle).

Table 3. Information collected during mortality events of adult female and neonatal pronghorn, as applicable. This information was used to assist with determining the cause-specific mortality of pronghorn.

General information	Carcass observations	Area observations
Date of investigation	Puncture wounds	Human sign
Time of investigation	Specific body parts eaten	Predator sign
Unique identification number	Teeth marks	Tracks present
Initial capture date	Carcass buried	Scat present
Date of last location	Wounds on rump/legs	Fresh snow/rain
Estimated age at death	Killed at or drug to site	Evidence of struggle
Carcass coordinates	Evidence of nursing	
Collar coordinates	Body length	
Sex	Right hind foot length	
Collar stationary time	Fawn's hoof growth	
Collar frequency		
Photos recorded		
Femur color		
Liver collected		
Other tissue collected		
Carcass collected		
Predator scat collected		

Annual and seasonal survival

We used the OISurv package (Diez 2013) in R 3.3.1 software (R core team 2016) to estimate annual survival of adult females. Animals were right-censored on the day of their death or loss of collar functionality (i.e., collar drop-off or cessation of transmitter operation). We estimated Kaplan-Meier survival functions for the entire data set, and separately for each of the three study years. In order to exclude the influence of capture-related stress on mortality risk of newly captured animals, study years were defined as the 12 month period beginning the month after capture. Thus study year 2014 covers April 1, 2014 through March 31, 2015; study year 2015 covers March 1, 2015 through February 29, 2016; and study year 2016 covers March 1, 2016 through November 30, 2016. The shorter coverage in 2016 is necessitated by reporting requirements. Because there were no mortalities observed from December through March except for four related to capture, we are confident that the results are comparable among all years. All animals alive and collared at the beginning of a study year were included in the survival estimate for that year.

We used a log-rank test (Diez 2013) to assess if adult survival varied among years or between animals with blood selenium concentrations above or below the 0.08 ppm threshold considered nutritionally suboptimal (O'Gara and Yoakum 2004). We also used a Cox proportional hazards analysis to test for an effect of blood

selenium concentration as a continuous variable, an effect of hoof length (as a metric of nutritional condition at time of capture), and an interaction between blood selenium concentration and hoof length.

We used the survival package (Therneau 2012) in R 3.3.1 software (R core team 2016) to estimate annual survival of fawns. We used Cox proportional hazards models to assess seven covariates of fawn survival: sex, year, handling time (minutes), body mass (kg), capture date, horizontal cover-99 cm at the capture site, and whether fawns were captured in agricultural or natural (e.g., sagebrush) habitat. We used Pearson's correlation to evaluate associations of covariates for fawns and did not assess additive models with correlated ($\geq \pm 0.50$) covariates. No covariates of fawn mortality risk were correlated ($r = -0.15$ – -0.12), except for capture date and handling time ($r = -0.57$).

Annual and seasonal movement rates

We started with 271,817 unique GPS locations of collared pronghorn ranging from 1 to 6 hour intervals. Locations were collected from one day post-capture to 31 October 2016, mortality, or the date a collar stopped. We created subsets of data including only locations separated by 1 or 6 hours; the 1 hour data were used to assess daily activity patterns and the 6 hour data to assess seasonal movement patterns.

We looked at daily movement patterns during three, 4-month periods of the year: March-June, July-October, and November-February. The first period corresponds to the pre-parturition and birthing period, while the second period corresponds to the months when females may be with (mobile) fawns. The last period roughly corresponds to the time when migrating pronghorn occupy their winter home ranges.

We defined a “migration” event as a shift in home-range centers from one month to the next by a distance substantially greater than the distance across the average summer home range. We used summer home ranges because some animals appeared to move throughout the winter, never settling in a single area that could be reasonably considered to be its winter home range. We defined summer home ranges by locations collected in June-August. We estimated the distance across a home range as the diameter of a circle equal in area to the minimum convex polygon surrounding summer locations. The mean diameter of summer home ranges was 7.4 km. We considered twice this distance rounded to the nearest kilometer (≈ 15 km), to be the threshold distance to define a migration event. Defining migration as we did previously (Duquette et al. 2015) is not appropriate for this year's analysis, because some animals collared in previous years used different winter home ranges between years.

We used a Chi-Square test to test for differences between years in the proportion of animals to migrate from summer to winter home ranges, and a t-test to test for differences in migration distances between years.

Herd demographics

During May–July 2014 and 2016, we opportunistically surveyed the sex and age demographics to provide additional insight to the productivity of pronghorn in the study area. We also collected these data to provide inputs for modeling pronghorn population growth, as done in Wyoming (Berger and Connor 2008). We conducted surveys both from vehicles and on foot during regular field

Figure 10. Pronghorn silhouette used to survey pronghorn herd demographics on foot.

activities. We counted the number of adult males, adult females, and fawns observed in each herd. When possible, we used photographic silhouettes of pronghorn (Montana Decoy Inc., Pennsylvania, USA; Figure 10) to move closer to herds to improve our ability to differentiate juvenile males from females, and fawns from juveniles. We considered yearlings as adults for both sexes as it is difficult to distinguish between those age classes. We differentiated males from females by presence of a black patch near the cheek of males. We calculated the demographic ratios within and across years, including fawn:doe and buck:doe. We tested for potential differences in demographic ratios between years using a Chi-square test with Yate's correction (Zar 1999). We used this correction factor to prevent overestimation of statistical significance for limited data collected in 2015.

Population growth

We developed a female-based, stage-based population projection matrix to estimate the post-breeding annual population growth (λ) of pronghorn from an estimated fawn and adult female survival and fecundity rates. We assumed a three stage matrix:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & F_a & F_a \\ S_j & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & S_a & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_a \end{bmatrix}$$

composed of elements for fecundity ($F_y =$ yearling, $F_a =$ adult) in the first row and age class-specific survival ($S_j =$ fawn, $S_a =$ yearling and adult) in subsequent off-diagonal rows. We estimated the fecundity rate for yearlings and adults as the product of $\frac{1}{2} \times$ the estimated pregnancy rate \times the number of fawns born per female \times fawn survival. In 2015, 88% of captured females were pregnant. We estimated that females gave birth to an average of 1.2-1.3 fawns based on observed fawn:doe ratios in 2015 (Duquette et al. 2015). Survival rates were set as the mean survival of radio-collared female fawns (0.60; $n = 18$) and GPS-collared adult females (0.71; $n = 45$) from 2014–2016.

We assumed fawns did not reproduce until they had survived their first winter and that pronghorn have a 1:1 sex ratio at birth (O'Gara and Yoakum 2004). To assess the population growth in the absence of mountain lions we used the same fawn survival and fecundity rates, but we recalculated the adult female survival rate excluding mountain lion predations.

We calculated the dominant eigenvalue of \mathbf{A} to give the expected long term population growth rate (λ). We conducted a sensitivity analysis of projected population growth rate to the parameters input into the model by recalculating λ after changing a parameter by 0.01, holding all other parameters constant. We then calculated the sensitivity for each parameter as the difference between the modified and original projected growth rates divided by 0.01, and the elasticity as the sensitivity divided by the original parameter value then multiplied by the original projected growth rate.

RESULTS

Adult female capture

During mid-February 2016 we captured and deployed GPS collars on 17 adult female pronghorn from several locations across the study area (Figure 11). Adult females were captured using a net gun fired from a helicopter over a three-day period. Mean handling time from capture to release was 8 minutes (range = 5–12). Mean hind foot length was 38.6 ± 0.6 cm ($n = 15$) and we collected a blood, fecal, and hair sample from all females. There was one mortality directly associated with capture efforts, an adult female that suffered a leg fracture and was euthanized.

Figure 11 Capture locations (triangles) of adult female pronghorn deployed with GPS collars in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016.

Physiological stress and nutritional condition

Blood serum analysis of adult females showed 64% of females in 2014, 18% in 2015, and 50% in 2016 had suboptimal concentrations of selenium (<0.08 ppm). Altogether, 41% ($n=46$) of females tested in this study had suboptimal selenium concentration (Table 4; Figure 12). There was no obvious spatial pattern in which animals had low selenium.

Table 4. Mean blood serum selenium or copper concentration parts-per-million (ppm) for adult female pronghorn in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016. Selenium concentration ≤ 0.08 ppm and copper concentration < 0.70 ppm are considered nutritionally suboptimal (O’Gara and Yoakum 2004). Estimates of blood serum copper concentration were not available in 2014 or 2016.

Year	Selenium (ppm)		Copper (ppm)	
	Mean \pm SD	Range	Mean \pm SD	Range
2014 ($n = 11$)	0.10 \pm 0.07	0.04-0.23	-	-
2015 ($n = 17$)	0.19 \pm 0.13	0.03-0.48	0.66 \pm 0.12	0.50-0.88
2016 ($n = 18$)	0.10 \pm 0.07	0.01-0.27	-	-
All years ($N = 46$)	0.15 \pm 0.11	0.03-0.48	0.66 \pm 0.12	0.50-0.88

Figure 12. Blood serum selenium concentration parts-per-million (ppm) for adult female pronghorn ($n = 46$) in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016. Selenium concentration ≤ 0.08 ppm is considered nutritionally suboptimal (O’Gara and Yoakum 2004).

Fawn capture

From 8–29 May 2016 we captured and processed 18 neonatal pronghorn (8 females and 10 males; Figure 13) consisting of two pairs of twins and 14 individual captures. Five fawns were captured near GPS cluster locations of adult females, with the remaining captured opportunistically. We confirmed birthing sites at an additional 11 cluster locations, but we were unable to capture fawns from these sites either due to their absence ($n=5$) or because the fawns were too large to catch on foot.

Mean fawn flush distance upon handler approach was 12 m (range = 0–150). Median body temperature of fawns in 2016 was 39.6 ± 0.6 °C and mean handling time was 8 ± 2 min (Table 5). Date of capture and handling time were negatively correlated ($r = -0.57$), indicating fawn handling time decreased over time. Body mass, body length, and hind foot length were the most correlated fawn morphometrics (Table 6). Median body mass of females (4.6 ± 0.7 kg; $n = 8$) was similar (Wilcoxon rank sum test; $W = 33.0$, $P = 0.88$) to males (4.8 ± 0.8 kg; $n = 10$) in 2016. Median body mass was similar between 2015 and 2016 for all fawns ($W = -0.46$, $P = 0.650$), females (Wilcoxon rank sum test; $W = -0.719$, $P = 0.484$), and males (Wilcoxon rank sum test; $W = -0.054$, $P = 0.958$). Eight fawns were released prior to collecting all morphometrics due to increasing body temperatures during handling. The only health complications observed during capture or handling was one female fawn that had abnormally low temperature (34.8 °C) upon initial capture. We classified five fawns as “slightly wobbly” and 13 as “very sturdy” during handling. We collected hair from 16 fawns for genetic banking.

Dominant land cover at fawn capture locations was comprised of graminoids (38%), forbs (26%), barren ground (18%), shrubs (15%), and coniferous forest (3%). In 2016, 78% of fawn capture locations were in natural habitats (e.g., sagebrush), compared to 38% in 2015. Captures in 2016 were also spaced more broadly across the landscape compared to 2015.

Figure 13. Capture locations (stars) of neonatal pronghorn ($n = 42$) in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2015-2016. Note that several captures on the “U” area of Clear Lake Wildlife Refuge and agricultural land immediately south of Alturas overlap and appear as single capture locations

Table 5. Median and interquartile range (IQR) of rectal temperature and morphometrics of neonatal pronghorn captured in May-June 2015 (n = 24) and 2016 (n = 18) in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California.

Year and Sex	Rectal temperature (°C)	IQR	Body mass (kg)	IQR	Body length (cm)	IQR	Chest girth (cm)	IQR	Hind foot length (cm)	IQR	New hoof growth (mm)	IQR
2015	39.6	1.6	4.4	0.9	63.5	4.5	39.0	3.3	27.0	2.8	2.4	1.1
Female	39.9	1.3	4.2	0.7	63.0	1.9	39.0	2.9	26.8	0.9	2.5	0.5
Male	39.5	1.3	4.4	0.7	64.0	7.5	39.0	3.5	28.0	3.0	1.9	1.0
2016	39.6	1.1	4.5	0.8	63.4	2.4	38.5	4.5	28.5	1.1	2.6	1.0
Female	39.5	1.3	4.5	0.9	64.0	2.3	38.5	3.0	29.0	0.8	2.5	0.6
Male	39.6	0.8	4.4	0.4	62.5	1.6	38.7	5.3	28.2	0.8	3.1	1.1
All years	39.6	1.3	4.4	0.7	63.5	4.5	39.0	3.5	28.0	2.0	2.5	1.1
Female	39.8	1.3	4.5	0.9	63.5	5.3	38.8	3.1	27.1	2.0	2.5	1.1
Male	39.6	1.3	4.4	0.9	63.5	6.0	39.0	3.8	28.0	2.0	2.3	1.1

Table 6. Correlation matrix of morphometrics neonatal pronghorn (n = 42) captured in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, May-June 2015–2016. Correlations ≥ 0.50 are highlighted in bold.

Metric	Weight (kg)	Body length	Chest girth
Body length (cm)	0.52		
Chest girth (cm)	0.58	0.30	
Hind foot length (cm)	0.67	0.28	0.56

Landscape-scale resource selection

In 2016, adult females strongly avoided forest, and to a lesser extent avoided riparian areas, agricultural habitat, and higher elevations, but selected locations in grassland-herbaceous and shrub habitats. During fall-winter 2016, adult females similarly avoided forest and to a lesser extent grassland-herbaceous and agricultural habitats, higher elevations, but selected locations closer to riparian areas and shrub habitat (Table 7).

Table 7. Resource selection of adult female pronghorn (n = 32) based on used locations and randomly selected locations annually, during spring-summer (April-September) or fall-winter (October-March) 2016, Modoc and Lassen Counties, California. Locations obtained from 2 adult females captured in 2014, 13 females in 2015, and 17 females in 2016. Resources presented with coefficients (β), standard errors (SE), and P-values from generalized linear models. Note that a negative coefficient for resources listed with distance suggests that resource was selected because used locations were closer to the resource.

Model	β	SE	P-value	R ²
Spring-Summer				
Forest (% locations)	-0.872	0.008	<0.001	
Grassland-Herbaceous (% locations)	0.509	0.005	<0.001	
Elevation (m)	-0.528	0.006	<0.001	
Dist. to primary-secondary roads (m)	-0.305	0.005	<0.001	
Dist. to tertiary road (m)	0.233	0.005	<0.001	
Agriculture (% locations)	-0.125	0.005	<0.001	
Shrub (% locations)	0.095	0.001	<0.001	
Dist. to riparian (m)	0.026	0.005	<0.001	
Fall-Winter				
Forest (% locations)	-0.980	0.011	<0.001	
Grassland-Herbaceous (% locations)	-2.010	0.063	<0.001	
Elevation (m)	-1.361	0.001	<0.001	
Dist. to primary-secondary roads (m)	0.858	0.009	<0.001	
Dist. to riparian (m)	-0.398	0.008	<0.001	
Dist. to tertiary road (m)	-0.424	0.011	<0.001	
Shrub (% locations)	0.247	0.008	<0.001	
Agriculture (% locations)	-0.010	0.001	0.417	

Landscape-scale resource selection of adult females across years suggested females consistently selected locations at lower elevations in riparian or herbaceous habitats, but avoided forest and woodland habitats (Table 8; Figure 14). While pronghorn locations were on average closer to primary-secondary roads than unused locations (Table 8), the mean distance of used locations from a primary-secondary road was still >9 km. Use of several habitats varied among seasons (Figure 14). Pronghorn used shrub lands more frequently in

the spring and winter months than during summer and fall months. Use of conifer woodlands, while always relatively low compared to availability of this habitat, was greater in spring than other seasons. In contrast, use of agricultural lands was consistently lowest in spring, even though overall use of agricultural lands varied widely among years. Use of riparian areas was greatest in the relatively hot and dry summer and fall seasons.

Table 8. Resource selection of adult female pronghorn ($n = 45$) based on used locations and randomly selected locations annually, during spring-summer (April-September) or fall-winter (October-March) 2014–2016, Modoc and Lassen Counties, California. Locations obtained from 11 adult females captured in 2014, 17 females in 2015, and 17 females in 2016. Resources presented with original scales and coefficients (β), standard errors (SE), and P-values from generalized linear models incorporating an interaction term of season and year. Resource statistical significance was set as: $\alpha = 0.05$. Note that a negative coefficient for resources listed with distance suggests that resource was selected because used locations were closer to the resource.

Model	β	SE	P-value	R ²
Forest (%)	-74.300	46.930	<0.001	0.11
Forest*Year	0.366	0.023	<0.001	
Forest*Season	2.436	0.082	<0.001	
Grassland-Herbaceous (%)	109.200	17.090	<0.001	0.09
Grassland-Herbaceous*Year	0.055	0.009	<0.001	
Grassland-Herbaceous*Season	-0.367	0.001	<0.001	
Dist. to riparian (m)	-1.003	0.015	<0.001	0.02
Riparian*Year	0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Riparian*Season	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Elevation (m)	-0.203	0.065	<0.001	0.02
Elevation*Year	-0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Elevation*Season	0.002	<0.001	<0.001	
Dist. to primary-secondary roads (m)	0.026	0.001	<0.001	0.01
Primary-secondary roads*Year	-0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Primary-secondary roads*Season	0.002	<0.001	<0.001	
Dist. to tertiary road (m)	-0.207	0.011	<0.001	0.01
Tertiary road*Year	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Tertiary roads*Season	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Shrubs (%)	-80.250	15.020	<0.001	0.01
Shrubs*Year	0.398	0.007	<0.001	
Shrubs*Season	0.143	0.015	<0.001	
Agriculture (%)	138.300	31.370	<0.001	<0.01
Agriculture*Year	-0.686	0.016	<0.001	
Agriculture*Season	-0.300	0.028	<0.001	

Figure 14. Fraction of pronghorn used and randomly selected locations in the study area in different habitat types. Bars show use in the spring, summer, fall and winter months separated by year. The first set of bars in each habitat category represents 2014, then 2015, and 2016. Solid black bar at the left of each category shows the availability of that habitat type in the study area estimated from 10,000 randomly generated points.

Home range resource selection

We completed a total of 501 habitat surveys, including 252 surveys of locations used by adult females and 249 unused locations (Appendix A). We completed 191, 171, and 139 habitat surveys in 2014, 2015, and 2016, respectively. Across years, 305 surveys were conducted during spring-summer (Apr-Sep) and 195 were conducted during fall-winter (Oct-Mar).

Adult female pronghorn used locations that, on average, were less obscured by tall shrubs (Figure 15), had more forbs, were more likely to be coincident with recent livestock activity, had less shrub cover, and were at 25 m higher elevations than nearby random locations (Table 9). There was not a significant difference in the proportion of used (4/33) versus nearby random (14/80) locations that were heavily wooded.

We opportunistically collected characteristics of 195 livestock fences throughout the focal study area. Of all fences characterized, 60% were ‘unpassable’ (i.e., lowest wire <16” from the ground) to pronghorn. Private landowners (79%), followed by the Bureau of Land Management (68%) owned the greatest percent of ‘unpassable’ fences (Figure 16).

Figure 15. Functional selection of horizontal shrub coverage at 99 cm height of 45 GPS-collared adult female pronghorn in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California during 2014–2016. The X-axis indicates the mean percentage of shrub coverage estimated in four directions from a point. The function selection is shown as the ratio of the fraction of used locations with a given level of shrub coverage to the fraction of random locations with that same coverage. Dashed line shows a ratio of 1:1 indicating that use was equal to availability. A ratio of >1:1 indicates selection for areas with a given level of shrub coverage and a ratio of <1:1 indicates avoidance of areas with a given level of shrub coverage.

Figure 16. Percent of ‘pronghorn passable’ livestock fences owned by each landowner, which are: Bureau of Land Management (BLM; n = 40), California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW; n = 8), US Fish and Wildlife Service (FWS; n = 4), Private landowners (n = 63), Pit River Tribes (PRT; n = 4), and US Forest Service (USFS; n = 76). A ‘passable’ fence had the lowest wire of any type ≥ 16 ” from the ground, with all other fences considered ‘unpassable’ (Cormack Gates et al. 2012).

Table 9. Habitat characteristics estimated at locations used by adult female pronghorn ($n = 45$) and randomly selected unused locations during spring-summer (April-September) or fall-winter (October-March) 2014-2016, Modoc and Lassen Counties, California. Locations obtained from 11 adult females captured in 2014, 17 females in 2015, and 17 females in 2016. P-values are from generalized linear mixed-models using year of survey fit to the intercept as a random effect.

Model	Used	SD	Random	SD	β_1	SE	P-value	β_{season}	SE	P-value	R ²
Horizontal cover-99 cm (%)	5.4	8.9	11.0	16.9	-0.551	0.133	<0.001	0.278	0.195	0.155	0.04
Elevation (m)	1480	70	1455	89	0.315	0.098	0.001	0.018	0.192	0.927	0.02
Shrubs (% transects)	19.4	29.6	29.5	35.4	-0.309	0.100	0.002	0.111	0.191	0.564	0.02
Forbs (% transects)	76.6	0.3	69.6	0.4	0.552	0.129	<0.001	0.006	0.194	0.978	0.01
Livestock activity (% locations)	28.8	45.8	17.5	38.1	0.301	0.096	0.002	-0.041	0.192	0.830	0.01
Active agriculture (% locations)	3.2	17.6	5.3	22.4	-1.000	0.094	0.284	0.102	0.191	0.592	0.01
Graminoids (% transects)	87.1	27.7	84.3	31.5	0.107	0.092	0.244	0.052	0.190	0.786	<0.01
Distance to nearest fence (m)	393	32	388	44	0.111	0.098	0.254	0.061	0.190	0.748	<0.01
Cheat grass (% transects)	19.4	0.4	23.9	41.0	-0.090	0.111	0.418	0.062	0.191	0.744	<0.01
Null	-	-	-	-	-0.038	0.181	0.832	0.059	0.189	0.755	-

Table 10. Habitat characteristics estimated at bed sites ($n = 34$) of neonatal pronghorn and randomly-selected nearby unused locations ($n = 34$) during May-July 2015–2016, Modoc and Lassen Counties, California. P-values are from generalized linear models.

Model	Used	SD	Random	SD	β_1	SE	P-value	β_{year}	SE	P-value	R ²
Horizontal cover-99 cm (%)	58.5	36.8	34.1	33.4	0.020	0.007	0.007	0.347	0.537	0.518	0.12
Graminoids (% transects)	69.6	40	86.5	32	1.327	0.717	0.064	-0.106	0.505	0.834	0.07
Cheat grass (% transects)	19.1	38	32.6	45	1.642	0.895	0.067	-0.976	0.745	0.190	0.05
Shrubs (% transects)	20.4	33	34.1	40	1.079	0.701	0.123	-0.109	0.503	0.828	0.04
Livestock activity (% locations)	11.8	33	19.4	40	0.586	0.701	0.404	-0.220	0.508	0.665	0.03
Elevation (m)	1409	114	1433	108	0.002	0.002	0.361	-0.086	0.501	0.864	0.02
Horizontal cover-53 cm (%)	30.9	30.9	26.3	28.1	-0.006	0.008	0.517	-0.033	0.493	0.947	0.01
Distance to nearest fence (m)	384	51	380	55	-0.002	0.005	0.760	-0.068	0.537	0.899	<0.01
Forbs (% transects)	89.7	28	88.9	22	-0.134	0.998	0.893	-0.010	0.494	0.984	<0.01
Null	-	-	-	-	<0.001	0.324	1.000	<0.001	0.489	1.000	-

Fawn bed sites

We completed habitat surveys at 15 neonate bed sites and 15 unused locations in 2016. We pooled data from 2015 and 2016 to provide greater inference to bed site selection, creating an overall sample of 34 bed sites and 34 unused sites. Bed sites were located in areas with greater horizontal cover at 70 m than nearby locations (Table 10). We did not find evidence that habitat variables influenced bed sites differently between years. There was not a significant difference in the proportion of plots that were heavily wooded at bed sites (2/15) or nearby points (2/13; $p>0.99$).

To account for the component of bed site selection that takes place at broader spatial scale, we also compared habitat characteristics of bed sites to the complete set of random points visited, regardless of whether the point was originally paired with a bed site or an adult use location ($n=249$). This larger set of random points can be considered to be a characterization of the landscape as a whole. Comparison of individual habitat variables was done using a t-test for continuous variables or Chi-Square test for presence/absence variables. Presence of cheat grass was analyzed using a Fishers Exact test because expected values were less than five, violating assumptions of the Chi-Square test.

Bed sites were, on average, better concealed by low brush, at lower elevation, and had greater forb abundance than the overall landscape (Table 11). Bed sites were less likely to have cheat grass and marginally less likely to have any shrubs or medusa grass compared to random locations on the landscape (Table 11). We did not find differences in either concealment by high brush or graminoid abundance between fawn beds and the overall landscape.

Table 11. *Habitat characteristics at bed sites compared to all random locations visited on the landscape, Modoc and Lassen Counties, California. Data on cheat grass and medusa head only available from a subset of locations.*

Variable	Used	SE	Random	SE	Statistic	p-value
Horizontal cover-99 cm (%)	33.5	5.9	36.7	2.2	$t=-0.5$	0.630
Graminoids (% transects)	10.8	1.1	12.1	0.3	$t=-1.08$	0.287
Cheat grass (#present/#plots)	8/15	NA	68/80	NA	Fishers Exact	0.010
Shrubs (#present/#plots)	12/31	NA	136/249	NA	ChiSq=2.8	0.094
Elevation (m)	1411.0	20.0	1454.0	5.7	$t=-2.1$	0.045
Horizontal cover-53 cm (%)	33.6	5.9	36.7	2.4	$t=3.73$	<0.001
Forbs (% transects)	13.4	0.8	9.9	0.4	$t=3.97$	<0.001
Medusa Head (#present/#plots)	5/15	NA	50/80	NA	ChiSq=4.4	0.034

Mortality causes

Adult females - Mountain lions were the leading cause of mortality in 2016 and across years (Table 12; Figure 17), with most known or suspected predations occurring during spring-summer (Figure 18). Confirmed and probable mountain lion predations in 2016 accounted for 59% of all mortalities, with confirmed mountain lion predations accounting for 41% of mortalities. Six of the adult females confirmed or likely predated by mountain lions had sub-optimal selenium concentrations. We associated two confirmed mountain lion and two coyote mortalities with capture myopathy as they occurred within 10 days of the capture (Table 12). After excluding capture-related predation mortalities, confirmed or suspected mountain lions kills accounted for 62% of all pronghorn mortalities and 80% of predation-related mortalities.

Table 12. Cause-specific mortality of GPS-collared adult female pronghorn captured in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016.

Contributing factor	2014	2015	2016	Combined
Mountain lion predation	2	1	3	6
Mountain lion probable	-	-	1	1
Mountain lion, Poor nutritional condition	-	1	-	1
Capture myopathy, Mountain lion predation	-	2	-	2
Coyote predation probable	-	1	-	1
Capture myopathy, Coyote predation	-	-	2	2
Predation (unknown) probable	1	-	-	1
Infection, Poor nutritional condition	-	1	-	1
Poaching probable	1	-	-	1
Unknown	-	-	1	1
Capture related stress (<i>also included above</i>)	-	2*	2*	4*
Total	4	6	7	17

*Not included in totals to avoid double counting because these mortalities also had other contributing factors and were included in those counts.

Figure 17. Cashed GPS-collared adult female pronghorn killed by a mountain lion in Lassen County, California, 2016.

Figure 18. Timing of pronghorn mortalities (n = 17) known or probably attributed to mountain lions in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016.

Fawns - Of the 18 fawns radio-collared in 2016, 10 (56%) died, consisting of six females and four males (Table 13; Figure 19). Most mortalities were attributed to unknown cause or probable coyote predations (Table 13). Similar to 2015, fawn mortalities occurred within 35 days (median = 9) after birth and all occurred on or before 3 July (Figure 20). We classified carcasses in deteriorated condition as having an unknown cause of death.

Table 13. Mortality causes of neonatal pronghorn captured in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, May-July 2015-2016.

Mortality cause	2015	2016	Combined
Unknown ¹	5	4	9
Probable coyote	-	4	4
Coyote predation	1	-	1
Bobcat predation	1	-	1
Combine harvester	3	-	3
Starvation, Poor nutritional condition	3	1	4
Unknown canid	-	1	1
Unknown predator	1	-	1
Total	14	10	24

¹ Mortalities were likely due to exposure to cold, disease or malnutrition, but we could not definitively determine this in the field.

Figure 19. Locations of neonatal pronghorn ($n = 18$) captured during May 2016 in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California. Locations in yellow are fawns that lived and in black are fawns that died between capture and 31 July 2016. Inset shows capture locations of six fawns on the “U” area of the Clear Lake Wildlife Refuge. Note: three fawns overlap capture locations of other fawns (none of which were mortalities) in the agricultural fields southwest of Alturas or at the south side of the Likely Tables.

Figure 20. Plot showing temporal capture and mortality events of neonatal pronghorn ($n = 42$) in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, May-July 2015-2016.

Annual and seasonal survival

Adult females - Average annual survival of adult female pronghorn was 69.6% (SE = 7.0%; Figure 21). Annual survival was similar ($X^2_1 = 0.20, P = 0.694$) among years (Figure 22). If confirmed/probable mountain lions predations ($n = 8$) are excluded, average annual survival of adult females increased to 83.7% (SE = 6.3%).

Figure 21. Cumulative annual survival rate (dashed lines = 95% confidence intervals) of adult female pronghorn ($n = 48$) monitored with GPS radiocollars in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California from 8 March 2014–30 November 2016.

Figure 22. Annual survival rates of adult female pronghorn monitored with GPS collars in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California from 1 April 2014–31 March 2015 ($n = 11$), 1 March–28 February 2015 ($n = 20$), and 1 March–30 November 2016 ($n = 32$). Two females monitored in 2014 were included in the 2015 risk set, and two and 13 females from 2014 and 2015, respectively, were included in the 2016 risk set.

Survival of females with suboptimal blood selenium concentration at time of capture was significantly lower than for other females ($X^2_1 = 3.4$, $P = 0.06$). Females with suboptimal blood selenium concentration also suffered higher predation rates than those not deficient in selenium (Figure 23). There was no indication that increasing selenium levels above the threshold improved survival probability ($p > 0.99$) or that hind foot length ($p > 0.4$) was correlated with survival.

Figure 23. Estimated annual predation risk of adult female pronghorn in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California with low or high blood selenium concentrations at time of capture.

Fawns - Average survival of fawns across years from date of capture through July 31 was 44.4% (SE = 7.8%; $n = 42$) and survival of fawns captured in 2015 was 44.1% (SE = 10.4%, Table 14). Fawn survival was similar ($\chi^2 < 0.10$, $P = 0.865$) between 2015 and 2016 (Figure 24). While estimated survival rates were higher for female fawns than male fawns in both years (Table 14), the difference was not significant given the small sample size and the large confidence intervals around each estimate (Figure 25). We found no evidence that other covariates tested influenced the risk of fawn mortality (Table 15).

Table 14. Kaplan-Meier survival estimates of radio-collared neonatal pronghorn ($n = 42$) captured in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2015–2016.

Year and Sex		Survival rate (%)	SE	n
2015	Female	67.5	15.5	10
	Male	28.6	12.1	14
2016	Female	50.0	17.7	8
	Male	40.0	15.5	10
All Years	Female	60.2	11.7	18
	Male	33.3	9.6	24
All Fawns	2015	44.1	10.4	24
	2016	44.4	11.7	18

Figure 24. Survival rates of neonatal pronghorn monitored with VHF radiocollars in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California during 2015 ($n = 24$; black line) and 2016 ($n = 18$; orange line). Dashed lines are 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 25. Survival rates of male ($n = 24$; black line) and female ($n = 18$; orange line) neonatal pronghorn monitored with VHF radiocollars in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California during 2015 and 2016. Dashed lines are 95% confidence intervals.

Table 15. Cox-proportional hazards models assessing covariates of seasonal mortality risk of radio-collared neonatal pronghorn ($n = 42$) in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2015–2016.

Model	β_1	SE	P -value	R^2
Sex * Year				8.2
Sex	187.990	186.000	0.312	
Year	0.701	0.765	0.359	
Sex : Year	-0.932	0.923	0.312	
Sex	0.695	0.454	0.125	5.8
Handling time (min)	-0.087	0.071	0.220	3.6
Capture habitat ¹	-0.338	0.422	0.424	1.5
Body mass (kg)	0.160	0.221	0.468	1.2
Capture date	<0.001	<0.001	0.843	<1.0
Horizontal cover-99 cm (%) ²	0.002	0.009	0.813	<1.0

¹Comparison of fawns captured in agricultural versus natural (e.g., sagebrush) habitat.

²Variable best explaining fawn bed site resource selection.

Movement rates

Daily movements were greatest from noon to about 19:00, averaging about 400 m/hr. (Figure 26). Daily movements were least during early and late morning hours, but activity was recorded at all times of the day. Temporal activity patterns were similar throughout the year, but pronghorn daytime movements tended to be longer in the winter than other seasons (Figure 26). This increase in activity rate corresponded into greater

distances between monthly activity centers in the winter (Figure 26: solid lines) and larger winter home ranges compared to other seasons. Activity centers varied least from one month to the next in the summer.

Figure 26. Daily activity patterns of adult female pronghorn ($n = 45$) monitored with GPS collars in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California during 9 March 2014–31 July 2016. Solid line is median hourly movement distance; dashed lines show the interquartile range and dotted lines show the 5th and 95th percentile of hourly distance moved at a given time.

We observed several putative migration events, where an individual shifted its home range center by at least 15 km from one month to the following month. Example migration paths are shown in Figures 27-29. Most migrations to winter ranges took place in November, while migration to summer ranges typically occurred in March and April (Figure 30). However, migration events were observed throughout the year, and we

observed a variety of migration behaviors over the course of the study. These include: rapid migrations, where transitions from one use area to another take place over the course of a few days; slow migrations occurring over several days or even weeks; round trip migrations where seasonal home ranges are in approximately the same area from one year to the next; and migrations where seasonal home ranges vary among years. A higher proportion of animals migrated to winter home ranges in fall 2015 (10/15) than in fall 2014 (1/5), and migration distances tended to be further in 2015 than in 2014 (Figure 31). Winter home ranges in consecutive years tended to be further apart on average than was the case for summer home ranges (Figure 31).

Figure 27 Locations of GPS-collared adult female pronghorn ($n = 3$) migrating from wintering grounds near Clear Lake, Modoc County, CA during 1 February–19 April 2016. Starting locations are shown as teal-colored triangles and their movement is shown over time as dots changing from yellow to black. Historical migration corridors are those identified by direct observation of a previous CDFW biologist during the 1970s, but should not be considered all-inclusive.

Figure 28 Locations of GPS-collared adult female pronghorn ($n = 3$) migrating from winter grounds on the Likely Tables or from spring-summer grounds in the Devil's Garden area, Modoc County, CA. Their movement (25 November–25 December 2015) to winter grounds is shown over time as dots changing from pink to dark purple, and movement (1 February–1 March 2016) to spring-summer grounds as yellow to black. Inset shows clustering of locations at the intersection of Highways 299 and 395. Historical migration corridors are those identified by direct observation of a previous CDFW biologist during the 1970s, but should not be considered all-inclusive.

Figure 29 Locations of GPS-collared adult female pronghorn ($n = 3$) migrating from wintering grounds near Smoke Creek Road, Lassen County, CA during 1 February–19 April 2016. Starting locations of females are shown as teal-colored triangles and their movement is shown over time as dots changing from yellow to black. Historical migration corridors are those identified by direct observation of a previous CDFW biologist during the 1970s, but should not be considered all-inclusive.

Figure 31. Timing of migration events. Each bar represents the number of times animals shifted their monthly home range center by ≥ 15 km from their home range center the previous month.

Figure 30. Distance between home range centers from season to season and year to year. Summer home range centers were determined from locations collected in July of that year. Winter home range centers were determined from locations collected in February of that year.

Female F05 provides an instructive example of the different kinds of migration patterns we have observed in this study. From her initial capture in March 2014 through the first week of April 2015, she occupied a single area and did not migrate during that year. Then, in April 2015 she moved 21 km northeast in one day, followed by another move 12 km northwest two weeks later. At the end of June she returned 12 km southeast to the area where she first migrated to, then in August she returned 21 km in one day to her original April use area. She remained there until December, when she migrated 30 km south in two days to a winter home range. She occupied that area until early February 2016 and then over the course of eleven days returned to her original April 2015 use area.

Herd demographics

During 14 June–14 July 2016 we opportunistically conducted a total of 153 herd demographic surveys. The fawn:doe ratio differed ($\chi^2_2 = 264.89$, $P < 0.001$) among years, with a >83% reduction in the fawn:doe ratio observed in 2016 compared to the previous two years (Table 16). The buck:doe ratio differed ($\chi^2_2 = 140.55$, $P = <0.001$) among years, with over 2.5 times as many bucks observed per doe in 2016 as in previous years (Table 16).

Table 16. Sex and age demographic estimates for pronghorn in Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016. Estimates based on opportunistic counts of herds.

Demographic count	Estimate (standard deviation)			
	2014	2015	2016	All
Herds counted	169	37	153	359
Mean herd size	9.3 (11.3)	18.1 (16.0)	6.7 (11.0)	8.3 (11.6)
Fawn:Doe	0.6:1 (0.8:1)	0.6:1 (0.9:1)	<0.1:1 (0.5:1)	0.4:1 (0.7:1)
Buck:Doe	0.3:1 (0.3:1)	0.3:1 (0.3:1)	0.8:1 (0.3:1)	0.5:1 (0.8:1)

Population growth model

Vital rates used to build the model are given in Table 17. This combination of vital rates predicted a long-term growth rate of $\lambda=0.95$, corresponding to a 5% annual decline in the population, and matched the observed population trajectory from 1993-2003. Population growth was by far the most sensitive to changes in adult survival. To achieve a growing population, birth rates or fawn survival would have to increase by 27% of the value observed in this study, while adult survival would have to increase by only 7% of its current value. Even maximizing pregnancy rates to 100% would not by itself lead to a growing population. If mountain lion predation were eliminated, the projected population growth rate would be $\lambda=1.10$, corresponding to a 10% annual increase.

Table 17. Parameter values used to build the pronghorn population model and measures of how changes in those demographic rates are predicted to influence population growth.

Parameter	Value	Sensitivity	Elasticity	λ at max possible value	Value required for $\lambda=1$
Pregnancy rate	0.88	0.20	0.183	0.976	-
Female fawns per pregnant female	0.64	0.30	0.200	1.05	0.81
Fawn survival	0.60	0.33	0.206	1.07	0.76
Adult survival	0.70	1.10	0.802	1.27	0.75

DISCUSSION

Demographic rates were relatively similar across years and indicate the pronghorn population was declining 5% per year. Adult mortality rates continued to be higher than observed in most pronghorn populations (Gaillard et al. 1998, Sawyer and Lindzey 2000, Bright and Hervert 2005, DeVos et al. 2005, Jacques et al. 2007, Berger and Conner 2008, Keller et al. 2013). The only examples we found in the literature of pronghorn populations that have adult mortality rates higher than our study, were from declining populations (Bender et al. 2013, Bright and Hervert 2005). In contrast, fawn survival rates on the Modoc Plateau were similar to or higher than those observed in other populations (Beale and Smith 1970, Barrett 1984, Fairbanks 1993, Sievers 2004, Berger and Conner 2008). As has been found in most other ungulate studies (reviewed by Gaillard et al. 2000), population dynamics were most sensitive to adult survival. Typical ungulate populations, are characterized by high and stable adult survival with high variability in fawn survival driving population fluctuations (Gaillard et al. 2000). However, the difference between a declining and growing pronghorn population on the Modoc Plateau appears to be associated with adult survival. Our model suggests that increasing adult female survival to >75%, still well below annual adult survival observed in most of the studies of other pronghorn populations cited above, is sufficient to lead to a growing population. We believe the key to recovering pronghorn on the Modoc Plateau rests with understanding why adult mortality rates are so high.

Mortality of adult pronghorn is associated with a variety of causes. In locations where hunting occurs, harvest can account for a large proportion of the sexes being taken (Jacques et al. 2007, Kolar et al. 2012). Predation accounted for a very minor proportion (1 -2%) of adult mortalities in some locations (Kolar et al. 2012, Bender et al. 2013), while in other studies predation is the predominant (59-70%) cause of adult deaths (Barnowe-Meyer et al. 2009, Keller et al. 2013). On the Modoc Plateau, we found that predation accounted for 10 (59%) adult female mortalities, excluding four predations that occurred shortly after capture and may have been capture-related. Across the three years of this study, mountain lions accounted for as much as 47% of all mortalities, and 80% of predator-related mortalities. Mountain lions accounted for 39% of known pronghorn mortalities in a South Dakota study (Keller et al. 2013), 14% of mortalities in Yellowstone National Park (Barnowe-Meyer et al. 2009) and 7% of mortalities in Arizona (Bright and Hervert 2005). The percentage of mortalities attributed to mountain lions on the Modoc Plateau exceeds what has been published elsewhere. Interestingly, coyote predation appears to be a larger issue for adult pronghorn at other study areas, ranging from 14% – 30% of mortalities of telemetered animals (Jacques et al. 2007, Barnowe-Meyer et al. 2009, Keller et al. 2013), while in our study site coyotes were responsible for only 10% of mortalities.

As described previously (Duquette et al. 2015), we would have predicted that in the open sagebrush-steppe habitat typically occupied by pronghorn, vulnerability to predation by ambush predators such as mountain lions would be low (Hornocker 1970, Logan and Sweanor 2001). However, other studies (e.g., Barnowe-Meyer et al. 2009, Keller et al. 2013) have also found that pronghorn are vulnerable to predation by mountain lions. Historic and current encroachment of woody vegetation into sagebrush-steppe habitat on the Modoc Plateau (Figure 32), may provide increased opportunity for mountain lions to ambush pronghorn. Drought may also be playing a role, forcing pronghorn to take increased risk by venturing closer to woody vegetation in search of more palatable forage. The location of most adult pronghorn predations observed in our study suggest that mountain lions are using the conifer woodland as cover to ambush pronghorn that venture close to that edge. If mountain lion populations are increasing on the Modoc Plateau (since being fully protected in 1990), or are switching to pronghorn due to decreasing populations of preferred or more vulnerable prey, risk to pronghorn may escalate with increasing juniper encroachment.

While mountain lions may impact pronghorn populations directly through predation, the presence of this large carnivore on the landscape may mitigate other impacts to pronghorn in general or at certain life stages. As mentioned above, coyote predation is frequently found to be a significant source of adult pronghorn mortality, and in some studies has been found to be the greatest cause of pronghorn mortality (e.g., Gregg et

al. 2001), accounting for 62% of fawn mortalities at the Hart Mountain National Antelope Refuge in southeastern Oregon (Dunbar et al. 1999). As part of an on-going study of mountain lion biology on the Modoc Plateau, we have documented a number of coyotes predated by lions (D. Garcelon, unpublished data), and coyotes have either been reported in the diet (Kertson et al. 2011) or to have been killed at food caches by mountain lions in other studies (Spalding and Lesowsk 1971, Koehler and Hornocker 1991). If mountain lions serve to reduce coyote density in areas where they overlap on the Modoc Plateau, this may provide some reduction in pronghorn fawn mortality from coyotes. In a study by Berger and Conner (2008), they found that in areas recolonized by wolves (*Canis lupus*) there was a 34% lower neonatal mortality rate in pronghorn, which resulted in a positive impact on pronghorn population dynamics. A negative correlation was found between coyote and wolf densities, suggesting that intraspecific interactions were decreasing coyote abundance where wolves were present (Berger et al. 2008). Mountain lions may be serving a similar role as wolves do in the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem, while perhaps not to the same extent, by lowering coyote densities on the Modoc Plateau.

Figure 32. Increase of western juniper from 1906 (a) to 2007 (b) on the XL Reservation along the North Fork of the Pit River, Modoc County, California. Source: Figures 3 and 4 in the U.S. Forest Service, Sage Steppe Ecosystem Restoration Strategy, Final Environmental Impact Statement (2008). Original access from Modoc National Forest History Archive (#62552) – Historic Photo Collection.

Seasonal Factors

We believe that pronghorn mortalities occurring in February and March were principally due to capture-related factors. However, the majority (7/13) of adult pronghorn deaths occurred in May, during the peak pronghorn parturition period, and in June when females were still closely associated with recently born offspring. Higher adult female mortality rates during this period have been reported in other studies (Bender et al. 2013, Keller et al. 2013), suggesting this seasonal increase in vulnerability may be a common feature of pronghorn populations. High vulnerability to predators during the fawning season may be because female pronghorn seek areas away from groups, and areas with higher cover, during the parturition period (Keller et al. 2013). In addition, the post-birthing and weaning stage places high energetic demands on pronghorn mothers and also focuses their activities in close proximity to their fawns, a behavior which may attract the attention of predators.

While our study was not designed to look at changes in pronghorn behavior during the fawning season, we can gain some insights by comparing habitat at locations used throughout the year to fawn bed sites (Figure 33). Adult female pronghorn locations not associated with fawn beds appear to be, on average, in areas with lower shrub coverage. In contrast, concealment by both short and tall shrubs at fawn beds was higher than at adult locations. Tall shrub coverage at bed sites was similar to random locations, while low shrub coverage at bed sites was substantially greater than at random locations. This combination suggests that pronghorn are selecting for low shrub cover, likely as a way to hide fawns from predators. However, to find sufficient concealment for fawn bed sites, females are moving into areas that have greater tall shrub covers than they would otherwise use. This behavior could also lead to the observed increase in use of shrub and conifer woodland habitats in spring relative to other seasons.

Figure 33. Habitat characteristics of pronghorn fawn bed sites (Bed), randomly chosen locations of GPS collared adult female pronghorns (Location) and randomly selected nearby points on the landscape (Random).

Possible Role of Selenium on Survival of Pronghorn

Selenium plays an important role in various physiological functions. Adequate levels are necessary for proper bone metabolism, blood formation, immune function, reproductive success, and iodine metabolism (Flueck et al. 2012). Along with other trace elements selenium is an important component of antioxidant enzymes that are used in preventing cellular damage (Saito et al. 2003; Flueck et al. 2012). Associating direct cause and effect of trace element deficiencies in free-ranging animals is challenging, and we are therefore relegated to

looking at correlations of measured values to observed differences in vital rates. Looking at a single trace element such as selenium is further complicated by interactions with vitamin E, which in sufficient supply can replace a portion of the role of selenium (Ullrey 1981). Therefore, adequate access to vitamin E in the environment may mitigate the consequences of reduced selenium intake. Further confounding interpretation of selenium concentrations in wildlife is that some species, such as mountain goats (*Oreamnos americanus*), may have a lower physiological requirement for the element as an adaptation for living in a low-selenium environment (Flueck et al. 2012). While collectively these factors complicate understanding how lower blood selenium concentrations might be impacting pronghorn, selenium deficiency is well-established as having deleterious impacts to domestic livestock, and therefore merits careful consideration as a health factor for pronghorn.

We observed lower survival in pronghorn with suboptimal blood selenium concentrations at the time of their capture. Most female predations occurred during the early post-fawning period. It has been reported that domestic cows (*Bos taurus*) will mobilize selenium, even in the case of deficiency, in their milk during early calf rearing (Serdaru et al. 2004). If this mechanism also occurs in pronghorn, adult females may be further selenium compromised during this post-parturition period. Whether any sub-clinical selenium deficiency might lead to reduced ability to escape predators (e.g., reduced muscle function, blood production) is unknown. Also, as we obtain our value for selenium in pronghorn during the winter, we do not know the status of their selenium concentration at the time of their death.

MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS

The Modoc Plateau pronghorn population had a higher annual mortality rate than reported for most other pronghorn populations, while fawn survival is similar to what has been reported in other non-declining populations. Mountain lion predation accounts for the greatest proportion of mortalities on telemetered female pronghorn. While pronghorn have historically persisted on the Modoc Plateau in the presence of mountain lions as predators, it is unknown how lion population size has fluctuated over time, and if there are more lions on the landscape than were present 100 years ago. Regardless of potential changes in mountain lion population size, we believe western juniper encroachment into sagebrush-steppe habitat has increased predation risk to pronghorn. The greater cover provided by the larger woody vegetation increases the opportunity for ambush hunters such as lions to get closer to pronghorn than they might be capable of in the absence of such vegetation (see Appendix D).

While there are limited options for directly managing mountain lion populations in California, landscape level approaches to habitat restoration may provide a more long-term solution. The State Wildlife Action Plan (CDFW 2015) supports restoration of habitat for sagebrush obligate species and both the USFS and the BLM have instituted clearing/thinning projects on the Modoc Plateau to reduce the extent of juniper in some areas. A joint interagency project to examine how wildlife respond to these treatments would be instructive in determining if this habitat restoration approach leads to reduced mortality in pronghorn.

Harvest of pronghorn in northeastern California only includes bucks (with the exception of a limited number of either-sex apprentice hunts), and that, combined with the apparently normal pregnancy rates observed in the population within the Likely Tables, Lassen and Clear Lake hunting units, suggests that the current harvest rates are not impacting the population.

A potential exception might be in the Big Valley and Mount Dome units. These units have experienced long-term downward trends based on aerial counts conducted by CDFW (Figure 34). Because our study did not include any telemetered females in these units, we do not know if the factors affecting the Likely Tables, Lassen, and Clear Lake units are the same population limiting factors at play in the Big Valley and Mount Dome units. From a management standpoint it would be informative and prudent to investigate what factors may be contributing to the apparent decline of pronghorn in those units. To accomplish this, we recommend

a two-pronged approach. First, we recommend focusing future demographic studies on comparison of habitat use, mortality rates and mortality causes between management units with apparently continuing population declines (i.e., Big Valley and Mount Dome) and management units with apparently stable populations in the past 5-10 years (e.g., Lassen). Our second recommendation is the resumption of annual aerial counts (or some other way of estimating population size) in all units every year in order to be sure that apparent changes in population size in each unit are not due to migration from summer ranges in one unit to winter ranges in another. For example, if pronghorn use a winter range in a specific unit one year during an aerial count, but winter in a different unit two years later when the first unit is surveyed again, it would appear as a population decline. The reverse would appear as a population increase, while in both cases there may have been no actual numeric change in the two units combined. Two observations from this study suggest that migration between units may confound interpretation of aerial surveys in this manner. First, we observed ten adult females with parts of their annual home ranges in multiple management units (Appendix E), and second, we observed a higher proportion of animals migrating to winter ranges last year compared to the first year of our study. Including all management units in annual population surveys is the best way to prevent the potentially confounding effects of year to year variation in the propensity and timing, of migration to winter ranges.

The low blood selenium concentrations found in 41% of the female pronghorn at time of capture, and the higher proportion of those females with low selenium that died during the study, suggest that further investigation into the possible relationship of selenium deficiency and increased mortality may be merited. As the selenium concentration of females at the time of their death is unknown, sampling hair or tissue of pronghorn carcasses would be instructive for determining if those concentrations might be a factor contributing to mortality.

Figure 34. Pronghorn population survey data collected by the California Department of Fish & Wildlife during aerial surveys in pronghorn hunting units. Panel A denotes raw count data. The non-connected points represent when the CDFW stopped surveying each unit each year. Panel B shows running 5-year averages of count data. Panel C is an index of change in population size in each unit since 1992. Vertical dashed line denotes start of population decline.

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APPENDIX A. Summary of habitat characteristics used to assess the seasonal home range-scale resource selection of adult female pronghorn, Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016. Labels for locations are: used by GPS collared adult females (Loc), used by feeding pronghorn (Opp), and randomly selected locations (Rand). Loc and Opp locations were pooled in analysis. Definitions for variables can be found in the Methods. Fall-winter is considered October-March and spring-summer is April-September.

Estimate	2014				2015				2016						
	Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer		Fall-Winter			Spring-Summer		Fall-Winter			Spring-Summer		
	Loc	Rand	Loc	Rand	Loc	Opp	Rand	Loc	Rand	Loc	Opp	Rand	Loc	Opp	Rand
Elevation (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Elevation (m; mean)	1512	1450	1490	1456	1470	1466	1462	1500	1471	1444	1409	1422	1420	1484	1449
Elevation (SD)	75	33	55	46	47	-	68	110	131	52	75	73	58	80	112
Horizontal cover-53 cm (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Horizontal cover-53 cm (%; mean)	3.5	5.0	6.8	8.1	2.8	3.0	8.1	7.0	20.6	3.7	0.6	6.4	0.9	10.3	12.6
Horizontal cover-53 cm (SD)	3.4	9.4	11.6	10.7	2.7	-	12.7	9.6	24.9	4.6	1.4	7.2	1.3	10.6	18.2
Horizontal cover-99 cm (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Horizontal cover-99 cm (%; mean)	5.1	8.8	14.8	25.3	9.0	25.0	32.4	19.5	59.9	11.7	6.5	35.3	11.9	26.5	46.9
Horizontal cover-99 cm (SD)	11.9	21.8	22.7	35.4	20.1	-	36.9	29.7	36.8	18.7	10.4	38.3	21.8	26.5	36.9
Active agriculture (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	51
Active agriculture (%; mean)	<1.0	<1.0	2.2	2.2	4.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	12.2	<1.0	16.7	4.5	<1.0	11.1	9.8
Active agriculture (SD)	<1.0	<1.0	14.9	14.7	19.8	-	<1.0	<1.0	33.1	<1.0	40.8	21.3	<1.0	32.0	30.0
Livestock activity (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	51
Livestock activity	22.7	26.5	62.9	43.5	6.0	-	0.0	18.5	16.3	6.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.5	11.8

Estimate	2014				2015				2016							
	Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer		Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer		Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer					
(%; mean)																
Livestock activity (SD)	42.9	44.8	48.6	50.1	24.0	-	0.0	39.6	37.3	25.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	39.6	32.5	
Fence present (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54	
Fence present (%; mean)	9.1	5.9	10.1	13.0	4.0	-	11.4	3.7	6.1	31.3	33.3	36.4	28.6	22.2	29.6	
Fence present (SD)	29.4	23.9	30.3	34.1	19.8	-	32.1	19.2	24.2	47.9	51.6	49.2	46.9	42.4	46.1	
Dist. to fence (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54	
Dist. to fence (m; mean)	401	401	401	401	395	401	400	401	401	372	341	358	369	382	359	
Dist. to fence (SD)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	28	-	8	<1.0	<1.0	57	92	78	62	38	70	
Fence passable (n)	2	2	9	6	2	-	5	-	3	5	2	8	4	6	16	
Fence passable (mean)	0.5	0.5	0.8	0.5	0.5	-	0.2	-	1.0	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.8	0.5	
Fence passable (SD)	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.5	0.7	-	0.4	-	<1.0	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.5	
Cheat grass (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54	
Cheat grass (%; mean)	<1.0	<1.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	100.0	8.3	<1.0	<1.0	82.3	83.3	78.4	72.6	61.5	71.6	
Cheat grass (SD)	<1.0	<1.0	0.0	0.0	24.0	-	27.0	<1.0	<1.0	35.9	40.8	35.8	45.1	38.6	40.3	
Medusahead grass (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54	
Medusahead grass (%; mean)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	6.0	100.0	6.8	<1.0	<1.0	80.8	52.8	63.7	79.7	57.4	39.2	
Medusahead grass (SD)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	24.0	-	25.5	<1.0	<1.0	40.1	45.3	42.5	40.4	42.1	44.5	

Estimate	2014				2015				2016						
	Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer		Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer		Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer				
Graminoids (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Graminoids (%; mean)	91.3	75.5	87.4	78.8	92.5	<1.0	94.1	98.5	93.4	73.4	54.2	85.2	75.6	85.7	77.8
Graminoids (SD)	24.0	35.4	24.1	31.4	24.6	-	22.1	6.5	23.7	40.2	41.5	30.6	40.9	27.6	38.2
Shrubs (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Shrubs (%; mean)	10.6	2.2	16.0	16.8	25.1	100.0	33.8	13.3	37.6	28.7	7.0	45.0	20.8	27.1	40.1
Shrubs (SD)	18.7	7.1	26.9	26.8	33.3	-	36.8	24.3	36.0	34.5	11.1	38.6	35.6	33.0	38.0
Forbs (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Forbs (%; mean)	43.1	29.9	57.9	36.0	87.5	100.0	87.8	94.8	80.8	100.0	100.0	99.2	96.4	96.6	86.1
Forbs (SD)	40.4	37.4	31.4	32.0	25.3	-	28.3	17.6	30.6	<1.0	<1.0	3.6	13.4	8.7	23.0
Juniper trees distance (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Juniper trees distance (m; mean)	401	401	401	401	354	77	338	310	264	309	365	252	272	262	220
Juniper trees distance (SD)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	117	-	136	128	175	106	50	136	134	133	167
Juniper trees in plot (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Juniper trees in plot (mean)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	9.0	1.9	<1.0	<1.0	1.9	<1.0	5.4	14.1	7.6	18.1
Juniper trees in plot (SD)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	-	12.7	<1.0	<1.0	5.1	<1.0	15.2	28.6	15.7	30.3
Old growth juniper trees (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54

Estimate	2014				2015				2016						
	Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer		Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer		Fall-Winter		Spring-Summer				
Old growth juniper trees (mean)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	0.3	0.1	<1.0	0.2
Old growth juniper trees (SD)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	-	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	0.8	0.5	<1.0	0.5
DBH of juniper trees (n)	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	3	-	7	5	9	23
DBH of juniper trees (cm; mean)	-	-	-	-	-	25.8	16.7	-	-	6.3	-	26.2	29.5	17.1	22.0
DBH of juniper trees (SD)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.6	-	15.9	18.3	13.8	14.6
Phase of juniper trees (n)	22	34	89	46	50	1	44	27	49	16	6	22	14	27	54
Phase of juniper trees (1-3; mean)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	0.0	1.5	0.1	<1.0	<1.0	0.5	0.3	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.9
Phase of juniper trees (SD)	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	0.1	-	0.5	<1.0	<1.0	0.6	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.8	1.0

APPENDIX B. Pearson correlation matrix of variables used to assess the home range-scale resource selection of adult female pronghorn, Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2014–2016. Definitions for variables can be found in the Methods. Positive or negative correlations >0.5 or <-0.5 are bolded.

	Elevation	Cover 53	Cover 99	Active Ag	Livestock	Fence	Fence Dist.	Fence Pass	Cheat	Medusa-head	Graminoid	Shrub	Forb	Juniper distance	Juniper #	Old juniper	Juniper DBH
Cover 53	-0.06																
Cover 99	0.02	0.45															
Active Ag	-0.21	0.30	0.08														
Livestock	0.08	-0.06	-0.11	-0.12													
Fence	-0.15	0.06	0.08	0.03	-0.04												
Fence dist.	0.16	-0.04	-0.09	-0.03	0.09	-0.65											
Fence pass.	0.10	-0.15	0.09	0.03	0.29	-	0.06										
Cheat	-0.21	-0.05	0.08	-0.11	-0.20	0.29	-0.41	-0.10									
Medusahead	-0.13	-0.07	-0.04	-0.10	-0.15	0.27	-0.38	-0.14	0.79								
Graminoid	0.20	-0.02	0.09	-0.27	0.07	-0.10	0.17	-0.03	-0.19	-0.18							
Shrub	0.19	0.20	0.51	-0.16	-0.12	-0.02	-0.04	0.18	0.11	0.02	0.20						
Forb	-0.10	0.02	0.10	0.08	-0.28	0.12	-0.16	-0.16	0.33	0.29	-0.04	0.09					
Juniper dist.	-0.38	0.06	-0.34	0.27	0.03	0.04	-0.03	-0.11	0.08	0.16	-0.38	-0.50	0.07				
Juniper #	0.11	0.02	0.27	-0.05	-0.08	0.08	-0.17	0.03	0.17	0.02	0.09	0.29	0.06	-0.48			
Old juniper	0.05	0.02	0.15	-0.03	-0.08	0.12	-0.24	0.02	0.14	0.06	0.07	0.20	0.05	-0.29	0.52		
Juniper DBH	-0.04	0.08	0.14	-	-0.07	0.04	-0.08	-0.37	-0.19	-0.19	0.02	0.20	0.00	-0.18	0.12	0.35	
Juniper phase	0.05	0.00	0.24	-0.08	-0.15	0.12	-0.21	-0.01	0.47	0.32	0.08	0.31	0.20	-0.54	0.77	0.41	0.11

APPENDIX C. Pearson correlation matrix of variables used to assess the resources selected for bed sites ($n = 34$) of neonatal (<7 d of age) pronghorn, Modoc and Lassen Counties, California, 2015–2016. Definitions for variables can be found in the Methods. Estimates with at least moderately positive or negative correlations are bolded.

	Elevation	Cover 53	Cover 99	Active Ag	Livestock	Fence Fence	Fence Dist.	Fence Pass	Cheat	Medusa-head	Graminoid	Shrub	Forb	Juniper distance	Juniper #	Old juniper	Juniper DBH
Cover 53	-0.27																
Cover 99	-0.14	0.43															
Active Ag	-0.51	0.53	0.09														
Livestock	0.27	-0.33	-0.33	-0.32													
Fence	-0.09	0.02	0.11	0.13	-0.18												
Fence dist.	0.11	0.03	-0.10	-0.17	0.16	-0.89											
Fence pass.	-0.32	-0.23	0.28	0.25	-	-	0.26										
Cheat	0.18	-0.36	-0.21	-0.26	0.17	0.12	-0.16	-0.30									
Medusahead	0.29	-0.27	-0.31	-0.32	0.31	0.03	-0.01	-0.38	0.76								
Graminoid	0.37	-0.31	0.07	-0.74	0.26	-0.07	0.07	-0.37	0.33	0.29							
Shrub	0.44	-0.05	0.35	-0.41	-0.19	-0.01	0.04	-0.17	0.09	-0.11	0.37						
Forb	-0.17	0.11	0.08	0.18	-0.20	0.08	-0.10	0.34	-0.29	-0.41	-0.24	0.12					
Juniper dist.	-0.40	0.14	-0.17	0.44	0.01	0.02	-0.09	-0.26	0.02	0.13	-0.38	-0.45	-0.11				
Juniper #	0.42	0.04	0.12	-0.19	-0.11	0.12	-0.16	-0.25	-0.01	-0.12	0.11	0.20	-0.01	-0.45			
Old juniper	0.34	0.16	-0.01	-0.13	-0.08	-0.07	0.06	-	-0.11	-0.08	0.10	0.17	-0.01	-0.31	0.58		
Juniper DBH	-0.06	0.33	0.47	-	-	0.21	-0.21	-	0.24	-	-0.58	-0.59	-0.54	-0.66	0.72	0.10	
Juniper phase	0.38	-0.02	0.06	-0.21	0.03	0.15	-0.18	-0.23	0.18	0.03	0.16	0.14	0.03	-0.48	0.90	0.47	0.80

APPENDIX D. Views of pronghorn mortalities sites associated with predation by mountain lions. Note proximity of woody vegetation, primarily juniper trees, to the mortality sites.

Appendix D. Views of pronghorn mortalities sites associated with predation by mountain lions. Note proximity of woody vegetation, primarily juniper trees, to the mortality sites.

Appendix D. Views of pronghorn mortalities sites not associated with predation by mountain lions. Note that these sites were still in the proximity of woody vegetation.

APPENDIX E. Adult female pronghorn locations with respect to pronghorn hunting management units.

